

Recommended citation

Malik, K., & Wickramasinghe, V. (2018). International technology transfer and developing country firms. XXIX ISPIM Innovation Conference, Stockholm, Sweden, 17-20 June.

<https://research.manchester.ac.uk/en/publications/international-technology-transfer-and-developing-country-firms/>

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International technology transfer and developing country firms

Abstract: We present some key challenges faced in the acquisition of new knowledge from international technology transfer (TT) projects, analysing this from the perspective of technology receiver firms based in Sri Lanka. Important aspects of the role of the technology recipient includes: the gap in skills and experience of engineers between the recipient firm and the technology sending firm (typically based in advanced economies); human resource implications linked to training and effective use of technology received; and impact on innovation capabilities development for the recipient firm. We collected empirical data via interviews with ten managers based in two large technology based firms in Sri Lanka. Our findings show that senior management must ensure key staff like production engineers and operational managers acquire business skills to complement technical skills. This should help management to select the individuals who could act as future TT project leaders in their firms.

Keywords: transfer challenges; developing country; training; innovation capabilities.

1 Introduction

Some industrial companies in developing countries have had to invest significant effort to embark on inter-firm technology transfer (TT) projects. This typically involves transfer of technology from a foreign collaborating firm to another firm as part of a TT agreement/ contract. Many management teams have faced a number of challenges associated with the diffusion of knowledge linked to TT projects across geographical boundaries (Sparrow et al, 2004). The technological knowledge can flow from the technology developers (sender) to the technology receivers through a variety of mechanisms, including trade in equipment, FDI, licensing agreements, R&D collaboration, turnkey contracts and people movement (Zhang and Gallagher, 2016).

Some important aspects of the role of the technology recipient in countries like Sri Lanka, have not yet been subjected to thorough empirical analysis (Ganesan and Kelsey, 2006), such as: the gap in skills and experience of engineers in the technology recipient firm and the technology sending firm (typically based in advanced economies); human resource implications linked to training and effective use of technology received (Wickramasinghe, 2013), and it's wider impact on innovation capabilities development of the recipient firm.

This paper is based on the following main objectives:

- (a) describe current international inter-firm technology transfer practices from the perspective of two major technology receiver firms based in Sri Lanka. Their main lines of business are telecommunications service and cable manufacturing.
- (b) analyze major challenges faced by the technology receivers, especially relating to gaps in skills and training of staff and how these firms attempt to effectively absorb knowledge from TT projects to help improve innovation capabilities.

2 Methodological approach

Data presented in this paper has been gathered from both secondary and primary sources. The secondary data was collected from a review of literature associated with the management of international technology transfer, with a particular focus on the technology recipient and some human resource implications including training. Our empirical data was collected from two large technology based firms in Sri Lanka. Located off the southern tip of

India this tropical island has a population of 22 million people. Site visits were undertaken to conduct semi-structured interviews with 10 managers across both firms. These were senior and middle management level staff (e.g. heads of departments such as Manufacturing or heads of new projects). One methodological challenge is access to managerial staff, as the interviewees had little familiarity of sharing their work experiences and opinions with academic researchers. The decision to use a qualitative research methodology was based on the fact that little is known about the phenomena under investigation, indicating that case studies would be an appropriate choice of methodology (Ghauri, 2004).

As part of our firm selection criteria, we conducted some preliminary research to identify Sri Lankan firms who have been involved in at least two international TT projects, because this enables one to probe underlying issues relating to experiences of individuals involved in more than one project whereby they might have acted differently with a current project as a result of an earlier project. The technology received should have been introduced to the manufacturing process plant of the firm or utilised within a new product offering. In addition, the technology transferred to the firm must have been in operation for at least two years. The two case study companies both employ approximately 1500 staff each in Sri Lanka.

3 Brief theoretical perspective

One major challenge for the effective management of international technology transfer relates to the ability of the technology recipient being able to fully absorb the knowledge transferred from the technology sender, especially in the context of the recipient being based in a developing country (Lema and Lema, 2013). Firms cannot access knowledge from international technology transfer initiatives passively. Importing technology requires enormous effort, especially with more complex technological systems (Malik, 2004).

Training in use of new technology that has been acquired through a TT project is often seen as a key facilitator for knowledge transfer, as this helps to build the technology recipient's capabilities for successful utilisation of the technology (Osman-Gani and Jacobs, 2005; Wickramasinghe, 2013). This can then ensure that the TT receiver company staff are able to apply new knowledge and skills learned from the project specific training to the job and the subsequent maintenance of the learning on the job to increase project performance (Aoki, 2008). This also links to the notion that training associated with TT projects can help to increase innovation capabilities inside technology receiving firms (Battistella et al, 2016).

Specific complexities associated with the transfer of knowledge across international organisational boundaries can often be difficult to resolve (Malik and Bergfeld, 2015). These complexities might occur due to differences in the technological infrastructure, educational differences, and attitudinal differences between home and host countries (Vora and Kostova, 2007). Such complexities can lead to cultural misinterpretation, which can obstruct the flow of knowledge and learning for the technology receiver unit (Oparaocha and Oparaocha, 2016).

4 Research findings from technology receiver firms based in Sri Lanka

As required by the companies interviewed, in order to preserve their anonymity, their names have been replaced with the following: (1) *TELECOM-SL* and (2) *CABLE-SL*. Both companies were interviewed through site visits on their premises. In this section we present some key insights obtained from the two firms studied.

Sri Lanka is an interesting country to study as it is a developing economy largely based on agriculture, services, and light industry, but requiring more innovation across all sectors to become internationally competitive. Industrial production as a percentage of total production is dominated by the following major sectors of the Sri Lankan economy: 'Food, Beverages and Tobacco products' (47%); 'Textiles, Wearing Apparel and Leather products' (23%); 'Chemical, Petroleum, Coal, Rubber and Plastic products' (16.3%); and 'Fabricated Metal Products, Machinery and Transport Equipment' (8.3%) (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2014).

TELECOM-SL insights

TELECOM-SL is Sri Lanka's largest mobile telecommunications network provider. This firm was previously a subsidiary of a larger Asian telecommunications company. TELECOM-SL has built up a reputation for being a technology exploiter, known for introducing modern technologies to Sri Lanka. Employing approximately 1500 staff, the majority of TELECOM-SL employees hold a Bachelors or post graduate degree qualification and the average age of company employees ranges from 25 to 30 years of age.

We obtained insights from TELECOM-SL regarding the firm's acquisition of some key technologies and knowledge from three foreign collaborating partner firms to help introduce 3G telecommunication services into

Sri Lanka around five years ago. Hence TELECOM-SL were the 'technology receiver' and the foreign collaborating firms are regarded as the 'technology senders' when we analyse this as an international inter-firm technology transfer project. The foreign partner firms are based in China, France and Sweden. Services advertised as 3G must usually comply with some international technical standards, including standards for reliability and speed (e.g. data transfer rates). This means the technology receiver has to carefully project manage the implementation of the 'technology transfer project' in order to ensure effective implementation for services offered to home market customers and complying with various international standards. Hence this increases the complexity of some of the knowledge that needs to be acquired and understood by the technology receiver firm.

One of the major challenges facing TELECOM-SL is a lack of professional skilled staff, partly due to a national level technology skills shortage. This firm invested in utilising existing employees to work on the 3G technology transfer project by upgrading their knowledge and technology skills. This firm has several functional areas and it decided to divide each functional area into two sub-areas of planning and operational. Therefore planning teams were responsible for planning and upgrading the existing technology network, whilst operational teams were responsible for execution, operation and maintenance of the technology being acquired as part of the technology transfer project. Here it is important to note that each operational team not only included TELECOM-SL staff, but also some experts from the three vendors (i.e. the technology sending firms). Staff mobility seemed to be an integral component for this TT project as some high ranked staff received training at the foreign partnering company premises. Other staff received local training in this project, which was delivered at the firm's own dedicated training academy. Our interview findings confirmed that all employees were generally well motivated to learn and get involved with this TT project since the technology being introduced was new to Sri Lanka at the time of the project implementation. Most employees believed that this training was also beneficial for their future job prospects and employability in the telecommunications industry and other related technology areas.

CABLE-SL insights

Employing approximately 1500 staff, CABLE-SL is a company that was established in the mid-1960s and the average age of company employees is 38 years. The company manufactures a variety of different cables for local and foreign markets. We obtained insights from CABLE-SL regarding the firm's acquisition of some key technological knowledge relating to the introduction of the 5S concept inside this traditional based cable manufacturing firm in Sri Lanka. The 5S concept was instrumental in the establishment of a model plant manufacturing facility in CABLE-SL, where the model plant was seen to be successful in achieving the overall 5S implementation project goals, which included education/ training for company staff in use of improved and more efficient cable manufacturing processes.

A committee was appointed to implement 5S inside CABLE-SL (i.e. a technological knowledge receiver unit). The committee members received some initial training from the 5S training provider firm based in Japan (i.e. technological knowledge sender firm). Later training was rolled out to all employees of CABLE-SL to help change their attitudes to accept 5S. This was seen as a major task since employees have to accept long-term benefits that the firm can obtain after 5S implementation. The committee also had to make considerable financial investment and effort in order to help provide training to company employees. One way to promote the importance of incorporating 5S into the CABLE-SL work units was to convey to employees the importance of acquiring new skills that would also become marketable in applying for future promotions and finding new external career opportunities. This aspect was also highly appreciated by the employees, which contributed to the successful role out of 5S concept. CABLE-SL later established a 5S training team to provide training to company staff on how to integrate the 5S concept across the firm. This training included monthly talks on 5S, training through arranged visits to other Sri Lankan firms who had already implemented 5S by listening to their experiences, and in-house experts and foreign experts providing ongoing training sessions. We learned that the foreign experts (from technological knowledge sender firm) were more prominent in providing training during the initial implementation phase of 5S in CABLE-SL.

CABLE-SL faced some challenges in the company wide implementation of 5S, especially with production operative staff, who at first seemed reluctant to implement 5S in their day-to-day work tasks. To overcome this barrier, for those operative staff who participated in some 5S training sessions, the firm encouraged these employees to implement at least two elements of the 5S concept into their day-to-day work (as an individual attempt or as part of a team attempt depending on the job task situation). Since employee involvement and participation is very important for the successful implementation of 5S, CABLE-SL decided to reward employees for their efforts, where some job level implementations were evaluated by a panel of judges and awarded cash prizes. However, at the initial stages of introducing the 5S concept, these rewards were too high. For example, an award of 5000 SL Rupees might only have resulted in a saving of worth 2000 SL Rupees. This had to be reassessed by the company later as it was not sustainable. Nevertheless, this cash prize initiative had attracted many

employees to participate in some training initiatives and implement certain aspects of the 5S concept at the individual or team level.

5 Key issues arising

One of the key findings from our TT project case studies relates to training of staff in the Sri Lankan receiver firms, and how to fully understand and use the technological knowledge that has been transferred to their site. For example, in order to fully absorb knowledge about new technologies received there has to be a basic level of technical preparedness (McKay, 2008) that enables staff at the receiver firm to fully comprehend different technical attributes of the new technology package/ concept in order to operate and interact with it successfully. We also note that the foreign based technology sending firms provided some initial training, delivered in different formats for the receiver firms. Some high ranked staff from one recipient firm went to the foreign vendor firm site to receive direct training relating to the TT project. Most other staff from receiver firms (from both cases) received training locally via following means: a dedicated training academy; on the job training when using the new knowledge transferred; some off the job simulated training; visits to other Sri Lankan firms who had already implemented the same technological systems to learn from their experiences. In one of our cases (TELECOM-SL), the technology being received was developed and delivered by three vendors (i.e. divided amongst three technology sending firms). This can occasionally create some challenges around assembling, testing and commissioning the equipment received as part of one TT project (Jagoda et al, 2010; Senadeera and Wickramasinghe, 2005). Although the receiver firm staff gain experience in operating and maintaining the new technology, the drawback is that they must rely on three different vendors for operational maintenance and after-sales service (e.g. spare parts provision) support. One knock on effect of this is that the TT receiver firm (TELECOM-SL) employees have not had sufficient opportunities to fully absorb the technology. They may be competent with some operation and simple maintenance tasks, but for all other more complex requirements they need to still call for expertise from the three different technology suppliers. This type of post TT project issue requires careful management when firms initially negotiate contracts for such projects, possibly as part of ongoing technical support and training provided by the technology sending organisation (Malm et al, 2016; Senadeera and Wickramasinghe, 2005).

The CABLE-SL case study highlights how the establishment of a model plant in one part of the firm's manufacturing facility can be used to implement a TT project, especially in terms of education/ training provision for company staff. As mentioned in the TELECOM-SL case, we also learned how a dedicated training academy inside the company helps to disseminate knowledge from a TT project. Although the establishment of model plant facilities and training academies inside of firms is not widespread in many developing country industrial firms, there is some merit for firms to consider prioritising this type of infrastructure investment as it can help with improving knowledge acquisition from TT projects and it helps to initiate knowledge dissemination to other parts of a firm.

A prominent lesson learned from the CABLE-SL case was the role of the foreign experts (from the TT project sender organisation) in providing a high level of training during initial implementation phase of the TT project, which was seen to be a positive outcome for CABLE-SL. However, one drawback with this TT project was that there was no evidence of the training provider (TT project sender) evaluating the learning outcomes of the training that they had provided as part of this TT project. It seems that the training provider's knowledge of specific cable manufacturing practices was relatively poor, and as a consequence, examples they used in some of the training sessions were not practical based examples that could be linked to impact of training for further improvements in some cable manufacturing processes. Hence we conclude that the training provider did not analyse CABLE-SL's firm specific attributes like the technical capabilities of the cable production lines and there could have been a better balance between theory and practical based training provided. Despite this challenge, CABLE-SL conducted in-house audits every month to monitor progress covering all departments/ units of the firm. Based on these reviews, the content and nature of internal training programmes was also modified to address any concerns arising. Later on, this firm appear to have successfully implemented many other quality/ standards based on the experiences of implementing the TT project. Subsequently CABLE-SL has been awarded several productivity awards in some national level competition.

Both of the TT project case studies from Sri Lankan firms also help illustrate some wider impacts of both projects in the form of innovation capabilities upgrading. This may be considered as one of the major drivers of upgrading the absorptive capacity of technology recipient firms in developing countries. Although this type of upgrading might be mainly associated with the utilisation of more sophisticated technologies on production lines, our findings, in line with other research (e.g. Medcof, 2007; Wickramasinghe, 2013), show that the building of

organisational and managerial capabilities is also crucial when leveraging utilisation of new technologies to help upgrade innovation capabilities.

6 Conclusion

For management teams in developing country technology receiver firms, they need to direct policy towards the development of infrastructure upgrade and technical training in the long run, rather than mainly focusing on benefits exclusively linked to boosting FDI and exports. Developing human resource capability within international TT projects is a key theme arising from our research. Hence senior management need to ensure that staff, such as production engineers and operational managers are encouraged to acquire some key business skills to complement technical skills. Subsequently this enables senior management to select individuals with this type of skills set to act as future TT project leaders in the technology receiver firm.

Our findings are exploratory. Hence, they provide a foundation to validate and examine the results through further research on international TT projects in Sri Lanka and other developing countries.

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